

100 Ma cycles of oceanic lithosphere generation in peri-Gondwana: Neoproterozoic-Devonian ophiolites from the African margin of Gondwana and the Variscan Orogen.

Ricardo Arenas^{1*}, Sonia Sánchez Martínez¹, Javier Fernández-Suárez¹, Pilar Andonaegui¹, Rubén Díez Fernández², Richard Albert³, Axel Gerdes³

¹Departamento de Mineralogía y Petrología e Instituto de Geociencias (UCM, CSIC), Universidad Complutense. 28040 Madrid, Spain.

³Departamento de Geodinámica, Universidad Complutense. 28040 Madrid, Spain.

⁴Institut für Geowissenschaften, Goethe-University Frankfurt, 60438 Frankfurt, Germany.

* Corresponding author at: Departamento de Mineralogía y Petrología e Instituto de Geociencias (UCM, CSIC). Facultad de Geología, Universidad Complutense de Madrid, C/ José Antonio Novais, no 2, 28040 Madrid, Spain. Tel.: +34 913944904

E-mail addresses:

arenas@geo.ucm.es (Ricardo Arenas, corresponding author)

s.sanchez@geo.ucm.es (Sonia Sánchez Martínez)

jfsuarez@ucm.es (Javier Fernández-Suárez)

andonaeg@geo.ucm.es (Pilar Andonaegui)

rudiez@ucm.es (Rubén Díez Fernández)

r.albert@ucm.es (Richard Albert)

gerdes@em.uni-frankfurt.de (Axel Gerdes)

Abstract

The Variscan Orogen and the Anti-Atlas mountains in Morocco contain a set of ophiolites formed between Neoproterozoic and Devonian times during the complex dynamics evolution of the African margin of Gondwana. It is accepted that during this temporary range that margin evolved from an active margin (c. 750-500 Ma, the Avalonian-Cadomian arc), to a passive margin that finally collided with Laurussia in Devonian times to form Pangea. In this context, the first recognized ophiolite is the Bou-Azzer Ophiolite from the Anti-Atlas, dated at c. 697 Ma and interpreted as oceanic lithosphere formed in a back-arc setting (El Hadi et al., 2010), although the geochemical composition of the mafic-ultramafic rocks of this ophiolite is poorly known. The Bou-Azzer back-arc closed probably some time later during collision of the volcanic arc with the main continent. More to the North, in the SW of the Iberian Massif, the Calzadilla Ophiolite contains mafic rocks of boninitic composition dated at c. 600 Ma (Arenas et al., 2018). The generation of this ophiolite is interpreted in relation to the opening of a fore-arc basin, deformed and eventually closed in Late Ediacaran times. Going farther North, in the NW Iberian Massif, the Vila de Cruces Ophiolite is formed by a thick sequence of mafic rocks with arc-tholeiitic composition and minor alternations of orthogneisses dated at c. 497 Ma (Arenas et al., 2007). This ophiolite was very likely formed during the opening of a new peri-Gondwanan back-arc basin, some time later closed or fill with siliciclastic sediments. Also in NW Iberia appears a group of ophiolites with a variety of lithologies and dominant mafic rocks with the composition of arc-tholeiites (ophiolites of Careón, Purrido and Moeche), dated at c. 395 Ma (Díaz García et al., 1999; Sánchez Martínez et al., 2011; Arenas et al., 2014a). These Devonian ophiolites represent the most characteristic group of ophiolites preserved along the Variscan Orogen. They were first

interpreted as remnants of the oceanic lithosphere formed in the realm of the Paleozoic Rheic Ocean (Sánchez Martínez et al., 2007), but some geochemical characteristics (isotopic Hf content in zircons) suggest that these ophiolites were more probably formed in a pull-apart basin opened after a first collision between Gondwana and Laurussia (Arenas et al., 2014b). Anyway the setting of this ophiolites is difficult to interpret as they have a clear synorogenic age.

Based on the ages of the described ophiolites, the peri-Gondwanan realm has been a domain where the generation of oceanic or transitional lithosphere occurred at intervals of 100 Ma, as the protoliths of these ophiolites were formed at c. 700, 600, 500 and 400 Ma. The first three ophiolites indicate generation of oceanic lithosphere formed in back-arc and fore-arc basins opened in relation to the complex dynamics of the peri-Gondwanan active margin. The meaning of the 400 Ma oceanic lithosphere is unclear considering its synorogenic formation, but it evolves anyway above the peri-Gondwanan upper mantle section (Arenas et al., 2014b; Díez Fernández et al., 2016), and then its origin is somehow also related to the previous setting linked to the evolution of a volcanic arc. It is commonly accepted that the generation of arc-tholeiites involves the decompression of a mantle wedge previously percolated by ascending fluids derived from the subducted oceanic crust. Boninites derive from similar sources after the generation of the arc-tholeiites. Different possibilities may perhaps explain the generation, and probable later removal, of oceanic lithosphere in the context of the African margin of Gondwana in repeated cycles of c. 100 Ma. However these constant time intervals probably also indicate rather constant rates for the generation of oceanic lithosphere in the peri-Gondwanan ridge at least between Cryogenian and Devonian times, as well as also a maintained rate of subduction below Gondwana during that period. The most evident effect of the generation of peri-Gondwan basins related to that long subduction, has been the growth towards the North of the continental margin of Gondwana during the considered temporary interval. Although difficult to interpret at present, it is very unlikely that the repetition of 4 cycles of generation of oceanic lithosphere at constant intervals is the result of a mere coincidence.

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